

Letter of publication

07-09-2022

Title: Management And Accounting: A Review From The Perspective Of
Costs

Manuscript

ID: JPSP-2022-0090

Dear *Maritza Montenegro González* , *José Orlando Levy* , *Jacinto Hernández Carranza*

It's our great pleasure to inform you that your above-mentioned manuscript has been reviewed and published in Journal of Positive School Psychology (JPSP) with ISSN 2717-7564.

Link: <https://www.journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/11305>

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With warm regards,
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